

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF A GdIII AND SmIII AMINO ACID COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION*

Ligand	SmIII		GdIII	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
Valine	5.24	5.04	5.10	4.80
Serine	4.92	3.86	4.66	4.13
Threonine	4.98	4.40	4.64	4.40
Methionine	5.04	4.70	4.93	4.38
Aspartic acid	5.89	4.92	5.65	5.22

* Limits of error ± 0.01 to 0.09 .

members of the series. This abnormal behaviour is known as 'gadolinium break'⁵.

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Ultraviolet Spectra of Diphenyl Sulphides, Polyphenylene Sulphides and Polyphenylene Ethers

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THE ultraviolet absorption spectrum of diphenyl sulphide was first recorded by Chaix¹ and later it was studied by several workers²⁻⁴. The compound gives two absorption maxima at 274 (ϵ 5700) and 250 nm (ϵ 11800). Finding that the explanations²⁻⁴ given by previous workers for the origin of the bands were at considerable variance, the present investigation was undertaken to make a deeper study of the problem.

The uv spectra of polyphenylene sulphides were also studied with a view to finding their absorption characteristics and to know how the observed bands change with lengthening of the molecule. A comparison of the spectra of polyphenylene ethers with

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their sulphur analogues was also thought of interest. Hence the required polyphenylene ethers were also prepared, their spectra recorded and analysed along with their sulphur analogues.

Experimental

Aryl methyl sulphides were obtained by methylating the corresponding thiophenols with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of alkali: methyl phenyl sulphide, b.p. 190–92° (lit.⁵ 195°/751 mm); methyl *o*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 104°/34 mm (lit.⁶ 96–97°/16 mm); methyl *m*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 110–12°/30 mm (lit.⁷ 110–12.5°/31 mm); methyl *p*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 212° (lit.⁸ 209°/747 mm); methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphide, b.p. 217–18° (lit.⁹ 217–18°).

Diphenyl sulphide was prepared following the reported procedure¹⁰, b.p. 162–63°/18 mm.

General method for the preparation of aryl phenyl sulphides: Freshly-cut sodium (0.1 g atom) was dissolved in absolute ethanol and thiophenol (0.1 mol) was added. Ethanol was then completely evaporated off and the solid aryl sodium was mixed with iodobenzene or the appropriate substituted iodobenzene (0.1 mol) and refluxed (220–30°) in an oil-bath for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was then acidified, treated with zinc dust (10 g) and steam-distilled to remove any unreacted iodo compound and thiol. The residue was ether-extracted, the extract dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and then ether evaporated off and the sulphide was distilled under reduced pressure: phenyl *o*-tolyl sulphide: b.p. 170–72°/22 mm (lit.¹¹ 160.5°/11 mm); phenyl *m*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 164°/10 mm (lit.¹¹ 164.5°/11 mm); phenyl *p*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 170–72°/20 mm (lit.¹¹ 167.5°/11 mm); *p*-chlorodiphenyl sulphide, b.p. 158–60°/7 mm (lit.⁴ 188°/35 mm); 2,2-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 64° (lit.¹² 64°); 2,2',6-trimethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 89–90° (lit.¹³ 89–90°); 2,2',6,6'-tetramethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 79–80° (lit.¹³ 79–80°); 2,2',6,6'-tetramethoxydiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 152–54° (lit.¹³ 152–54°).

Polyphenylene compounds: The known compounds were prepared according to the reported methods; 1,4-diphenoxybenzene¹⁴, m.p. 76–77°; bis(phenoxyphenyl) ether¹⁴, m.p. 108–09°; bis(*p*-phenoxyphenyl) ether of *p*-hydroxyquinone¹⁵, m.p. 149–50°; 1,4-diphenylthiobenzene¹⁶, m.p. 79–80°; *m*-diphenoxybenzene¹⁴, m.p. 61°.

Bis(p-phenylthiophenyl)sulphide: It was obtained from *p,p'*-dibromodiphenyl sulphide and phenyl sodium sulphide. The required *p,p'*-dibromodiphenyl sulphide was prepared by adding a solution of bromine (18 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) to a solution of diphenyl sulphide (18.6 g) in glacial acetic acid with shaking. The mixture was left for a few hours for complete bromination. The dibromo compound was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 111–12°.

It was reacted with phenyl sodium sulphide to obtain bis(*p*-phenylthiophenyl) sulphide, which was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, (50%), m.p. 99–100° (Found : C, 71.4; H, 4.8. C₂₄H₁₈S₂ calcd. for : C, 71.6; H, 4.5%).

Bis(p-phenylsulphonylphenyl)sulphone : It was obtained by the oxidation of the foregoing sulphide with KMnO₄, and then recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 298–300° (Found : C, 57.7; H, 3.9. C₂₄H₁₈O₆S₃ calcd. for : C, 57.8; H, 3.6%).

1,4-Di(p-phenylthio)phenylthiobenzene : It was prepared by the bromination of 1,4-diphenylthiobenzene as described for the preparation of *p,p'*-dibromodiphenyl sulphide. In this case the mixture was heated on a water-bath for some time to complete bromination and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (80%), m.p. 155–56° (Found : C, 47.4; H, 2.6. C₁₈H₁₂Br₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 47.8; H, 2.7%). It was mixed with phenyl sodium sulphide and heated with copper bronze for 5 h. The reaction mixture was washed free of alkali and digested with boiling ethanol repeatedly to remove any soluble matter. The residue, on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid or benzene, gave the title compound, m.p. 128–29° (Found : C, 70.4; H, 4.1. C₃₀H₂₂S₄ calcd. for : C, 70.6; H, 4.3%).

1,4-Di(p-bromophenylsulphonyl)benzene : It was obtained by oxidising the corresponding sulphide with KMnO₄ in acetic acid, and then recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 286–88° (Found : C, 47.7; H, 2.0. C₁₈H₁₂Br₂O₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 47.9; H, 2.3%).

1,4-Di(p-bromophenylsulphonyl)benzene : It was prepared by the KMnO₄ oxidation of 1,4-di(*p*-phenylthio)phenylthiobenzene in glacial acetic acid, and then recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. >300° (Found : C, 56.1; H, 3.3. C₃₀H₂₂O₈S₄ calcd. for : C, 56.4; H, 3.5%).

1,3-Di(phenylthio)benzene : It was prepared from *m*-dibromobenzene¹⁷ and phenyl sodium sulphide, (50%), b.p. 227–28°/16 mm (Found : C, 73.2; H, 4.7. C₁₈H₁₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 73.5; H, 4.8%).

The spectra were determined with a Hilger-Watts H.700.308 Uvispek spectrophotometer equipped with a silica prism. The solvent was cyclohexane unless specified.

Results and Discussion

A study of the spectra of a number of methyl aryl sulphides and diaryl sulphides seemed to be necessary to know more about the 250 and 274 nm bands of diphenyl sulphide and to fix their origin. The spectral data (Table 1) while indicate that two bands are present in the spectra of for all diaryl sulphides, the longwave band seems to be missing in the spectra of aryl methyl sulphides. But an examination of the spectral curves (Fig. 1) shows that this band does appear as a shoulder with a lower intensity in aryl methyl sulphides

TABLE 1—UV SPECTRA* OF DIARYL SULPHIDES AND METHYL PHENYL SULPHIDES

Sulphide	R=Ph		R=Me	
	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$	ϵ_{\max}	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$	ϵ_{\max}
C ₆ H ₅ .SR	278 252	5 700 12 400	255	6 900
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .SR	277 252	5 700 13 100	252	8 400
<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .SR	276 251	4 500 10 600	257	7 800
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .SR	278 252	6 000 12 100	257	9 600
<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .SR	281 256	5 900 10 600	262	13 800
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .SR	273 252	7 500 14 000	259	8 300
2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .SR	276 253	4 700 15 400	270	2 000

*In cyclohexane.

also. This observation makes it clear that the frequency of electronic excitation for the longwave band is considerably reduced in aryl methyl sulphides due to the absence of the second benzene ring but the band appears at about the same region as a shoulder. The complete absence of the 250 nm band in the spectrum of methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphide (Fig. 2) indicates the existence of a strong steric effect in the molecule, suppressing the conjugation responsible for the electronic excitation giving rise to this band. It can only be di-*ortho*-methyl substitution which prevents sulphur-benzene conjugation that requires coplanarity of -SCH₃ with the benzene ring. Thus it is clear that this conjugation involving electron-donation by sulphur to benzene ring is the origin of the 250 nm band. The presence of the longwave band in methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphide should then be due to another type of conjugation for which coplanarity of -SMe with the benzene ring is not necessary. This is benzene-sulphur conjugation, involving electron-acceptance by sulphur. Atoms having vacant *d*-orbitals can participate in such *d*-orbital resonance. Evidence for this type of conjugation, involving the formation of a (*p-d*) π -bond between ring carbon and sulphur, exists from dipole moments^{9,18}, kinetics of H-D exchange¹⁹ and ir intensities^{20,21}.

The increase in the ϵ_{\max} of the shortwave band of methyl *p*-chlorophenyl sulphide (Table 1) can be explained on the basis that when sulphur acts as an electron-donor, the *p*-Cl atom becomes an electron-acceptor expanding its valency shell as it has vacant *d*-orbitals²².

An examination of the spectral characteristics of diaryl sulphides (Table 2) and a look at the spectral curves (Fig. 3) throw more light on the origin of the two bands. All the diphenyl sulphides with two, three or even four *ortho*-substituents show the lower intensity longwave band. The higher intensity shortwave band at or near 250 nm is seen only as a

NOTES

Fig. 1. Spectra of methyl aryl sulphides and diaryl sulphides

Fig 2 Spectra of methyl phenyl sulphides

shoulder in the case of the fully *ortho*-substituted 2,6,2',6',-tetramethyl and 2,6,2',6'-tetramethoxy

TABLE 2—UV SPECTRA* OF DIARYL SULPHIDES

Sulphide	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$	ϵ_{\max}
Unsubstituted	274	5 500
	250	12 200
2,2'-Dimethyl	274	5 000
	248	12 000
4,4'-Dimethyl	276	6 800
	252	14 500
2,6,2'-Trimethyl	276	4 600
	249	13 900
2,6,2',6'-Tetramethyl	273	10 900
	257sh	8 300
2,2'-Dimethoxy	288	7 600
	248	11 300
2,6,2',6'-Tetramethoxy	284	10 600
	261sh	7 700

*In ethanol sh=Shoulder.

compounds with ϵ_{\max} very much reduced. They have even a higher ϵ_{\max} for the longwave band, which suggests that when the frequency of electronic

Fig. 3. Spectra of diaryl sulphides.

excitation causing the 250 nm band diminishes due to steric inhibition of resonance, the frequency of electronic excitation giving rise to the other band increases. It is also clear that the longwave band is not subject to the steric effect, as it arises from phenyl-sulphur conjugation (*d*-orbital resonance).

The above findings not only establish the incorrectness of the views expressed by Koch² and Mangini and Passerini⁴ but also remove the indefiniteness in the view of Fehnel and Carmack³ as to which type of conjugation gives rise to which band.

Polyphenylene sulphides and oxides: The polyphenylene sulphides (Table 3) show two absorption bands (Fig. 4), one at 285 nm and the other around

Fig. 4. Spectra of polyphenylene sulphides.

TABLE 3—UV SPECTRA OF POLYPHENYLENE ETHERS AND SULPHIDES*

Compd	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max}	No. of S or O atoms (n)	ϵ_{\max}^{**} %
$C_6H_5SC_6H_4SC_6H_5$	285	15 400	2	7 700
	262	18 200		9 100
$C_6H_5S(C_6H_4S)_2C_6H_5$	285	23 500	3	7 800
	265	27 000		9 000
$C_6H_5S(C_6H_4S)_3C_6H_5$	285	31 700	4	7 900
	267	35 900		9 000
$C_6H_5OC_6H_4OC_6H_5$	279	2 900	2	8 500
	272	3 300		
	238	17 000		
$C_6H_5O(C_6H_4O)_2C_6H_5$	279	4 900	3	8 400
	272	5 100		
	240	25 300		
$C_6H_5O(C_6H_4O)_3C_6H_5$	279	9 900	4	8 600
	272	10 000		
	243	34 500		
<i>m</i> -Diphenylthiobenzene	279	11 300		
	254	22 000		
<i>m</i> -Diphenoxybenzene	279	3 400		
	272	3 450		
	215	26 200		

*Oxygen or sulphur atoms para to each other unless specified **Corrected to the nearest hundred.

265 nm. A bathochromic shift of 11 nm occurs in the longwave band of $C_6H_5SC_6H_4SC_6H_5$ in comparison with that of $C_6H_5SC_6H_5$. Thereafter lengthening of the molecule has no effect on λ_{\max} ; the ϵ_{\max} increases with lengthening of the molecule. For the shortwave band, the bathochromic shift is 12 nm as we move from $C_6H_5SC_6H_5$ to $C_6H_5SC_6H_4SC_6H_5$. Thereafter as the chain length increases, the band undergoes a slight bathochromic shift with increase in ϵ_{\max} .

The origin of the two bands of the polyphenylene sulphides seems to be the same as that of diphenyl

sulphide. This view gains support from the fact that the absorption bands shown by polyphenylene ethers also correspond to those observed for diphenyl ether (λ_{\max} 279, 272, 227 nm; ϵ_{\max} 1 800, 2 000, 9 300, respectively Table 3). The two low intensity bands at 279 and 272 nm correspond to the vibrational bands of the benzenoid spectrum and their positions remain remarkably unchanged. The more intense shortwave band (227–243 nm) is due to oxygen-benzene conjugation. This is seen to undergo a small bathochromic shift as the length of the molecule increases. A striking resemblance exists between this band and the shorter wavelength band of diphenyl sulphide, both arising from the same type of conjugation. The second band seen for sulphides is not seen for oxygen compounds, as *d*-orbital resonance is not possible for the latter.

An interesting feature of the spectral data (Table 3) is that for each of the conjugation bands the ratio of ϵ_{\max} to the number of sulphur or oxygen atoms present in the molecule is almost constant. This principle is not applicable to the vibrational bands of benzene. It is also not applicable to *m*-diphenylthiobenzene and *m*-diphenoxybenzene.

While a regularity is found in the increase of λ_{\max} and ϵ_{\max} for parapolyphenylene ethers and sulphides as the chainlength increases (S or O from 2 to 4), the same regularity is not found as we move from the first member of each series to the next member. This may be due to the presence of $-\text{S}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{S}-$ or $-\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{O}-$ unit in the polyphenylene compounds and its absence in the first member of the series.

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Reaction of Steroidal Epoxide with Nitriles

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A number of oxazoline derivatives have been found to possess various biological activities¹ and a multidirectional applicability in several industries². Hence, an attempt has been made to synthesise the steroidal oxazoline from steroidal epoxide by a simple method. The configuration of oxazoline ring in **2** has been confirmed by ¹H nmr and also by its drying model.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (a) PhCN, BF₃-etherate, 25°,
(b) CH₃CN, BF₃-etherate, 25°

Scheme 2